

“AM I READY?”: COLLEGE PREPAREDNESS AS INFLUENCED BY ENGLISH PROFICIENCY AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

College preparedness is a crucial factor in ensuring students' success in higher education. This study aimed to determine the extent of college preparedness among Grade 12 students and how it is influenced by their English proficiency and academic performance. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, with 100 Grade 12 General Academic Strand (GAS) students from Tapaz West Secondary School selected through random sampling for the School Year 2024-2025. To measure college preparedness, a researcher-made questionnaire was developed. English proficiency was assessed using a standardized instrument evaluating the four macro skills: reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Meanwhile, academic performance was measured using students' 1st Semester General Average. Findings revealed that students, regardless of their academic performance and English proficiency, demonstrated similar levels of college preparedness. However, results also indicated that students with stronger English skills tend to perform better academically. Overall, students exhibited an average level of English proficiency and a very satisfactory level of academic performance. The extent of their college preparedness was high, and while no significant differences were observed in their levels of preparedness, significant relationships were found between English proficiency and academic performance.

Keywords: *College Preparedness, English Proficiency, Academic Performance, Standardized Test, General Average*

INTRODUCTION

College readiness is a crucial factor in determining a student's success in higher education. It encompasses various academic, cognitive, and non-cognitive skills, with English proficiency and academic performance playing significant roles. As English is widely used as the medium of instruction in many institutions, students who struggle with English proficiency may face difficulties in understanding course materials, communicating effectively, and performing well in assessments. Similarly, academic performance in high school serves as a predictor of a student's ability to cope with the demands of college-level coursework (Baber,2019).

A college degree can indeed serve as a gateway to both career advancement and personal development. Beyond the technical knowledge gained, higher education fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability—skills that are crucial for navigating the complexities of the modern world. The value of education is not only in the job opportunities it provides but also in how it enriches one's ability to make informed decisions, contribute meaningfully to society, and build resilience in the face of challenges. Ultimately, it is both a tool and a mindset that can guide individuals toward long-term success and fulfillment (Asio,2023).

Region VI- Western Visayas, has adopted the new K-12 program known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" through Republic Act No. 10533. The Department of Education (DepEd) graduated its first batch of senior high school graduates in 2018. However, there is a need to examine the college readiness of these graduates because some studies show alarming picture of the K to 12 students' performance. Learning English is indeed crucial for students as it serves as a vital international communication tool. To this day, senior high school students use the new English curriculum. However, English speaking seems very difficult for most Filipino students, especially at the secondary level, even though it is used as a second language in the Philippines. It is a common challenge for students, particularly in non-English-speaking environments, to struggle with English language. For senior high school students, this struggle can be particularly pronounced in tasks like essay writing and reflection, where clear and effective expression of ideas is crucial (Hibatulla, 2019).

In the District of Tapaz West, particularly in barangay schools, students often struggle with English as a medium of instruction. English proficiency remains a challenge for many Senior High School (SHS) students, affecting their ability to comprehend lessons, express ideas effectively, and engage in academic discussions. This struggle is rooted in various factors, including limited exposure to English outside the classroom, lack of confidence in using the language, and inconsistencies in language instruction throughout their schooling years.

Teachers and school administrators recognize that English proficiency is a key determinant of college readiness. The ability to read, write, and communicate effectively in English is crucial, as most tertiary education institutions use English as the primary language of instruction. Academic performance is another significant factor in determining college preparedness. Students who perform well in high school generally develop study habits, critical thinking skills, and discipline that prepare them for the rigors of higher education. However, if English proficiency is weak, even high-performing students may struggle in college, particularly in subjects that require strong language skills, such as research, literature, and technical writing.

Given these challenges, this study seeks to explore the extent to which English proficiency influences academic performance and overall college preparedness among Senior High School students in Tapaz West Secondary Schools. By understanding the connection between these factors, educators and policymakers can develop targeted interventions, such as remedial English programs, enhanced language instruction, and additional academic support, to better prepare students for tertiary education. This research aims to contribute valuable insights that can help improve the educational system and ensure that Senior High School graduates are competent and ready for the next stage of their academic journey.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students as influenced by English Proficiency and Academic Performance.

1. What is the level of English Proficiency skills of Grade 12 students of Camburanan, Candelaria, San Nicolas and Tapaz National High School in terms of listening, speaking, reading and writing?
2. What is the level of Academic Performance of Grade 12 Students of Camburanan, Candelaria, San Nicolas and Tapaz National High School?
3. What is the extent of college preparedness of Grade 12 students of Camburanan, Candelaria, Sa Nicolas and Tapaz National High School?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of college preparedness of Grade 12 students when classified according to the levels of English proficiency?
5. Is there a significant difference in the extent of college preparedness of Grade 12 students when classified according to the levels of academic performance?
6. Are there a significant relationships among English proficiency, academic performance and college preparedness of Grade 12 Students of Camburanan, Candelaria, San Nicolas and Tapaz National High School?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research employed descriptive-correlational. It aimed to determine the extent of College Preparedness among Grade 12 students of Tapaz West Secondary Schools for the School Year 2024-2025 as influenced by English Proficiency and Academic Performance.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in Tapaz West Secondary Schools namely, Camburanan, Candelaria, San Nicolas and Tapaz National High School which is located at Tapaz, Capiz, Philippines.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were one-hundred (100) Grade 12 General Academic Strand (GAS) students of Tapaz West Secondary Schools, enrolled for the school year 2024-2025. Respondents were taken through random sampling method.

Research Instrument

Adopted Instrument, specifically the standardized proficiency test assessing the four macro skills which are reading, listening, speaking and writing was used to measure the English Proficiency of the respondents. A researcher made instrument intended to test the college preparedness was developed. The researcher constructed forty-item questionnaire, presented to the panel of experts for face and content validity and undergo pilot testing at Rev. Tomas Conejar National High School.

Another important data collected in this study was the General Average of the respondents for the first semester of the school year 2024-2025. This academic performance measure was obtained from their advisers and served as a key indicator of the students' overall scholastic achievement.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured permission from the principals of Camburanan, Candelaria, San Nicolas, and Tapaz National High School to conduct the study and collect necessary data. A written request outlining the study's objectives and required data was submitted. The primary data collected was the General Average of Grade 12 students in the first semester, serving as a key indicator of their academic performance and college preparedness. Ethical considerations, including confidentiality and approval from school authorities, were strictly followed.

A researcher-made instrument underwent pilot testing to ensure reliability. A Standardized English Proficiency Test was administered to 100 Grade 12 students, assessing their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Additionally, a validated questionnaire was developed to measure college preparedness. After finalizing the instruments, the researcher sought permission from Tapaz West Secondary Principals and secured parental consent for student participation. The test and questionnaire were administered with the assistance of English teachers.

The study was conducted during the first semester of the School Year 2024-2025. The English Proficiency Test consisted of forty items, with listening, reading, speaking, and writing sections. Listening involved recorded conversations, reading included passage-based questions, speaking required students to express opinions within a given time, and writing involved composing an opinion-based response using rubrics for evaluation. The collected data was processed and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative Data Analysis

English Proficiency Level of the respondents

Table 1 shows the result of the English Proficiency Level of the respondents that were classified into four categories. In Listening Test (M=5.77) students have an “average” level, Reading Test (M=5.86) students have an “average” level, Speaking Test (M=5.70) students have an “average” level, and in Writing Test (M=6.08) students have a “high” level. This means that they can understand and communicate in English at a moderate level but may still struggle with more complex or advanced language use in these areas. However, their writing proficiency is higher compared to the other skills, suggesting that they may be more comfortable expressing ideas in written form, structuring sentences, and following grammar rules than they are in spoken or receptive skills.

As a whole the English Proficiency level of the students is “average” (M=5.85). This further implies that students have moderate skills in Listening, Reading, Speaking and Writing. Thus, students have to be exposed to more reading activities and engage in listening and speaking exercises.

The result affirms the findings of Rustamova (2023) incorporating diverse reading materials—such as literature, news articles, and academic texts—into the curriculum can foster a love for reading and promote language development. Teachers can implement guided reading sessions, where learners are encouraged to summarize texts, discuss themes, and reflect on the author's intent. This not only builds comprehension skills but also connects language learning with cultural and societal issues.

Additionally, Reading English books contributes most to the level of the speaking skills of the students' other factors such as using social networking sites and listening to English songs also have significant influence to speaking skills. Thus, the use of English movies on lectures in writing is recommended. It may be used as springboard or as evaluation activities. English teachers may also incorporate the use of social media, and different books during class discussion and activities. Speaking and writing skills are an important part of communication (Juayong- Caldoza & Cruz,2023).

Table 1
The English Proficiency Level of The Respondents

Category	Mean	Description
Whole	5.85	Average
Listening	5.77	Average
Reading	5.86	Average
Speaking	5.70	Average
Writing	6.08	High
Scale		
Mean		Description
8.01 – 10.00		Very High
6.01 – 8.00		High
4.01 – 6.00		Average
2.01 – 4.00		Low
0.00 – 2.00		Very Low

The Academic Performance Level of Respondents

Table 2 shows the level of Academic Performance of the respondents. Based on the 1st Semester General Point Average, it reveals that students have a 'very satisfactory' (M=88.63) Academic Performance. This suggest that a significant majority of the students have achieved high grades or have exceeded the minimum requirements for satisfactory academic performance and it creates pathways to further educational opportunities, and a solid foundation for future career prospects. It also suggests that the student is likely to possess valuable skills such as perseverance, discipline, and resilience, which contribute to their overall personal and academic development.

This can be seen on the study conducted by Dogan (2017). Motivation is a predictor of academic performance. Thus, motivation is essential in academic performance. Higher motivation also results in higher academic achievement (Kori et al., 2016). With this, motivation is likely to have a significant relationship with academic performance. The extent to which academic performance is affected by student engagement, academic self-efficacy, and academic motivation was evaluated.

Table 2
The Academic Performance Level of Respondents

Category	Mean	Description
Whole	88.63	Very Satisfactory
Mean		Description
90.00 - 100.00		Outstanding
85.00 - 89.99		Very Satisfactory
80.00 – 84.99		Satisfactory
75.00 - 79.99		Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75.00		Did not meet Expectations

The Extent of College Preparedness of the Respondents

Table 3 shows that the extent of college preparedness of the respondents is “High” (M=4.28). This high preparedness level may correlate with a greater likelihood of pursuing higher education goals. The data suggests a readiness that bodes well for both individual success and the broader educational landscape.

This can be affirmed on the study conducted by Othman et al. (2013) which suggests that academic aspiration may be influenced by both internal and external factors should be regarded as a fundamental component of the desire to succeed, functioning in life similar to a self-fulfilling prophecy, supported by Duncheon (2015) states that college preparedness include not only an emphasis on the perception of core academic content but also a focus on cognitive skills, non-cognitive skills, and learning strategies.

Table 3
The Extent of College Preparedness of the Respondents

Category	Mean	Description
Whole	4.28	High
Mean		Description
4.51 – 5.00		Very High
3.51 – 4.50		High
2.51 – 3.50		Average
1.51 – 2.50		Low
1.00 – 1.50		Very Low

Inferential Data Analysis

The Extent of College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students When Classified According to The Levels of English Proficiency

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference in the extent of college preparedness of grade 12 students when classified according to the levels of English Proficiency. This is also means, that variations in English Proficiency among students do not appear to have a meaningful impact on their preparedness for college.

Yung and Cai's study (2020) revealed that high English proficiency students as indicated by English test results did not automatically connected in the readiness and success of the students. These takeaways of college readiness have led the K to 12 Program stakeholders to delve on how to adequately prepare students in transitioning from high school to higher education with the ultimate goal of succeeding in their chosen careers.

Table 4
The Kruskal Wallis H Test Results in Testing the Significance of the Differences in The Extent of College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students When Classified According to The Levels of English Proficiency

Compared groups	N	Mean Rank	df	χ^2	Sig.
English Proficiency			2	2.340	0.310
Very High	1	31.00			
High	35	45.30			
Average	64	53.65			
Total	100				

P<0.5, not significant at 0.05 alpha

The Extent of College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students When Classified According to The Levels of Academic Performance

Table 5 shows that there is no significant difference in the extent of College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students when Classified According to the Levels of Academic Performance. It implies that students with varying levels of academic performance, whether outstanding, very satisfactory, or satisfactory, may experience similar levels of preparedness for college despite their differing academic standings.

Farrington (2012) stated that measure of GPA includes more than academic knowledge as it incorporates perseverance, compliance, and time management. It is also indicative of students' ability to collaborate with others, to communicate their ideas, and even to create products. Moreover, the course requirements or completion is another index of college readiness (Roderick et al.,2009).

In addition, College preparedness is meaningful if social capital is also considered. Social capital is critical to college readiness because it represents a student's awareness of college admission proceedings and methods for success when entering higher education. That is to say, students that possess the social capital for college typically have the knowledge to confront the complicated admission process and comprehend the college culture and standards (Roderick et al., 2009).

Table 5
The Mann-Whitney U Test Results in Testing the Significance of the Differences The Extent of College Preparedness of Grade 12 Students When Classified According to The Levels of Academic Performance

Compared groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum Rank	of Z	Sig.
Academic Performance				1.432	0.152
Outstanding	36	44.97	1619.00		
Very Satisfactory	64	53.61	3431.00		
Total	100				

P>0.5, not significant at 0.05 alpha

The Relationship Among the English Proficiency, Academic Performance and College Preparedness of The Respondents

The Spearman's Rho result in Table 6 reveals a significant relationship between English proficiency and academic performance ($r = 0.741$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that students with higher English proficiency tend to perform better academically. This finding highlights the crucial role of language skills in academic success, as proficiency in English may enhance comprehension, critical thinking, and communication in various subjects.

However, the correlation between English proficiency and college preparedness ($r = 0.127$, $p = 0.208$) and between academic performance and college preparedness ($r = 0.115$, $p = 0.255$) are not statistically significant. This implies that neither English proficiency nor academic performance alone can reliably predict a student's level of preparedness for college. These results suggest that other factors, such as study habits, motivation, and external support systems, may influence a student's readiness for higher education.

The results of a study conducted by Sahragard et al. (2011) demonstrated that students who scored higher on the language proficiency test had better GPA scores. Another study found that English language proficiency and academic performance are directly related (Aina et al., 2013; AlHaddad et al., 2004; Kumar, 2014; Xu, 1991). Along similar lines, students' achievement in school also depends upon their level of proficiency in the language of instruction (Wilkinson & Silliman, 2008).

In addition, the results of a correlational study conducted by Sahragard and Baharloo (2009) found that students who are more competent in the English language are more successful in their classes. Maleki and Zangani (2007) found a significant connection between proficiency and grade point averages of academic achievement among EFL students majoring in English translation, while Sadeghi et al. (2013) found that proficiency in English could significantly influence academic achievement.

Table 6
The Spearman’s Rho Results for Testing the Significance of The Relationship Among the English Proficiency, Academic Performance and College Preparedness of The Respondents

Variables N = 125	1		2		3	
	<i>r</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
1. English Proficiency	-		-		-	
2. Academic Performance	0.741***	0.000	-		-	
3. College Preparedness	0.127	0.208	0.115	0.255	-	

***p<0.001

Conclusions

In view of the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn.

The respondents have an 'average' level of English proficiency in listening, reading, and speaking, while their proficiency in writing is 'high'. Their ability to understand spoken and written English and communicate verbally is moderate, but they perform better when expressing their thoughts in written form. The overall level of their English Proficiency is 'average' which means they are capable of communicating in English to a certain extent but will benefit from additional support and instruction to enhance their skills further.

The academic performance level of the respondents is 'very satisfactory' it generally indicates that the respondents have achieved a level of performance that meets or exceeds expectations in their educational activities and they are doing well in their studies and are on track for success in their educational endeavors.

The extent of college preparedness of the respondents is 'High'. This implies that the respondents are well-equipped to succeed in a college environment, both academically and socially.

There is no significant difference in the extent of college preparedness of the grade 12 students as influenced by English proficiency. This suggests that a student's level of English proficiency does not have a direct or substantial impact on their preparedness for college. A high level of English proficiency may help students in areas such as reading comprehension, writing essays, and understanding lectures, but it does not necessarily guarantee that they are well-prepared for the overall demands of college life.

There is no significant difference in the extent of college preparedness of the grade 12 students as influenced by academic performance. This implies that a student's level of academic achievement does not necessarily determine their preparedness for college. While strong academic performance may indicate proficiency in subject areas, it does not fully capture other essential skills required for a successful transition to higher education.

There are significant relationships between English proficiency and academic performance of Grade 12 students of Camburuanan, Candelaria, San Nicolas and Tapaz National High School. This implies that students with higher English proficiency tend to achieve better academic performance.

Recommendations

In view of the foregoing findings and generalizations, the researcher suggested the following courses of action:

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Department of Education (DepEd), especially their officials and curriculum planners, can utilize this study in developing and enhancing essential learning competencies. They can pinpoint areas where students may require additional support and identify gaps in the existing curriculum that may be improved through policy revisions or instructional enhancements.

Grade 12 students should continue to engage actively in their studies while also seeking ways to deepen their understanding of the material. Establishing effective study habits, such as time management and regular revision, will further enhance their performance and educational institutions should continue to support and enhance their academic programs to maintain this high standard.

Incoming first-year college students, should prioritize sustaining their academic performance and improving their English proficiency as they transition into higher education. Utilizing the curated English handbook can be an effective tool for further enhancing their language skills and preparing them for the demands of tertiary education.

Institution should implement a holistic approach to readiness by focusing on study habits, critical thinking, time management, and problem-solving skills. Providing college readiness workshops, mentoring programs, and academic support services can help students develop the necessary skills for higher education.

Schools should focus on developing essential life skills, implementing college readiness programs, such as career guidance activities can help students transition smoothly to higher education. Additionally, encouraging independent learning, time management, and resilience-building activities will equip students with the necessary skills to succeed in college, regardless of their academic standing.

Future researchers are encouraged to build upon this study by exploring additional aspects of college preparedness, particularly focusing on the effectiveness of various instructional tools and resources in enhancing students' language proficiency. Conducting comparative studies between different methods of delivering language instruction—such as handbooks, online modules, workshops, and blended learning approaches—can provide valuable insights into the most effective strategies for preparing students for tertiary education.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher strictly followed ethical guidelines and standards applicable to educational studies. All participants provided informed consent, confirming their voluntary involvement in the study. Measures were taken to uphold confidentiality and anonymity, ensuring that the identities of participants remained protected throughout the research process. The study was conducted with integrity, utilizing the collected data exclusively for research purposes while ensuring no harm came to any participant. Furthermore, the research adhered to ethical principles of transparency, fairness, and respect for participants' rights.

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